

Synthesis of Some New Benzoxazole, Benzthiazole and Benzimidazole Derivatives with Biological Activity

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2-(N-Arylcarboxamidomethyl thio)-benzoxazoles (3), -benzthiazoles (4) and -benzimidazoles (5) have been synthesised by the reaction of 2a, 2b and 2c with different amines in presence of EEDQ as condensing agent. The structures were elucidated via another route of preparation. Cyclisation of 5 in pyridine and acetic anhydride furnished 2-N-aryl aminothiazolo [3, 2-a] benzimidazoles (6). Oxidation of (3b, k, f and l) with hydrogen peroxide gave the corresponding sulphones (7a-d), respectively. The biological activity of some compounds were screened against some bacteria and fungi.

It is well known that simple amides such as 2-phenyl-2-hydroxypropionamide¹ and N-benzyl-β-chloropropionamide², possess anticonvulsant activity. Also, acetamides, in which amido-H has been substituted by aromatic³ moieties have been synthesised in large number as potential local anaesthetics. The biological efficacy of benzoxazole⁴⁻⁶, benzthiazole⁷⁻⁹ and benzimidazole^{10,11} derivatives are also of interest. Consequently, the preparation of N-aryl substituted acetamides, containing thiobenzoxazolyl, thiobenzthiazolyl and thiobenzimidazolyl moieties was our objective in the hope that biologically interesting compounds might evolve.

Experimental

The purity of the prepared compounds was checked by tlc using benzene-ethylacetate mixture (9 : 1). IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 200 G spectrophotometer. Melting points are uncorrected.

2-(N-Arylcarboxamidomethyl thio)-benzoxazoles (3), -benzthiazoles (4) and -benzimidazoles (5) :

(a) N-Ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxy-1,2-dihydroquinoline (0.00025 mole) was added portionwise to a mixture of 2a, 2b or 2c (0.0002 mole) and the appropriate aromatic amine (0.0002 mole) in dimethylformamide (10 ml) at room temperature during 10 min. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hr, the solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the crude was crystallised from ethanol, yield about 50-60%. The results are listed in Table 1.

(b) To a solution of thiol compounds Ia, Ib or Ic (0.01 mole) in ethanol (15 ml) in presence of equivalent amount of KOH, was added N-aryl-2-chloroacetamide (0.01 mole) and the mixture was refluxed for about 20 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitate formed was filtered,

TABLE 1—2-(N-ARYLCARBOXAMIDOMETHYL THIO)-BENZOXAZOLE (3), -BENZTHIAZOLES (4) AND -BENZIMIDAZOLES (5)

Compd. No.	m.p. °C	Analysis% : Calcd./Found			
		C	H	N	S
3a	173-74	63.38	4.22	9.85	11.26
		62.91	4.11	9.46	11.71
3b	178-79	49.58	3.03	7.71	8.81
		49.11	3.46	7.61	8.22
3c	165-166	56.51	3.45	8.79	10.04
		56.71	3.41	8.82	10.16
3d	183-84	60.00	4.00	9.33	10.66
		60.31	4.21	9.61	10.21
3e	186-187	61.14	4.45	8.91	10.19
		61.26	4.61	8.17	10.85
3f	169-70	54.71	3.34	15.75	9.72
		54.51	3.12	15.66	9.66
3g	209-210	62.57	4.29	8.58	9.81
		62.11	4.18	8.18	9.51
3h	158-59	64.42	4.69	9.99	10.73
		64.23	4.41	9.21	10.41
3j	159-60	68.26	4.19	8.38	9.58
		68.16	4.61	8.22	9.51
3k	149-150	68.26	4.19	8.38	9.58
		68.21	4.41	8.12	9.47
3l	234-35	58.53	6.65	8.53	9.75
		58.18	6.36	8.41	9.36
3m	100-101	56.51	3.45	8.79	10.04
		56.18	3.28	8.60	10.21
3n	164-165	54.71	3.34	15.75	9.72
		54.61	3.31	15.21	9.66
4a	110-11	60.00	4.00	9.33	21.33
		60.22	4.11	9.21	21.11
4b	148-44	47.49	2.90	7.38	16.86
		47.21	2.61	7.31	16.41
4c	125-26	53.81	2.28	8.37	19.13
		53.61	3.26	8.33	19.61
4e	123-24	58.18	4.24	8.48	19.39
		58.16	4.21	8.18	19.31
4f	164-65	52.17	3.18	12.17	18.55
		52.16	3.22	12.16	18.51
4g	119-20	59.64	4.09	8.18	18.71
		59.41	4.22	8.41	18.61
4h	132-33	61.14	4.45	8.91	20.38
		61.22	4.61	8.81	20.11
4i	114-15	61.14	4.45	8.91	20.38
		61.66	4.26	8.18	20.21
4j	138-39	65.14	4.00	8.00	18.28
		65.22	4.21	8.41	18.11

TABLE 2—2-N-ARYL AMINOTHIAZOL[3,2-a]-
BENZIMIDAZOLES (6)

Compd. No.	m.p. °C	Analysis% , Calcd./Found			
		C	H	N	S
6a	197-98	67.90	4.15	15.8	12.10
		67.51	4.00	15.6	11.80
6b	229-30	52.30	2.90	12.21	9.30
		52.62	2.81	12.02	9.13
6c	227	—	—	14.00	10.68
		—	—	13.89	10.46
6e	195-96	65.08	4.41	14.24	10.85
		64.88	4.26	14.12	10.56
6f	255-56	58.10	3.20	18.10	10.30
		57.80	3.03	17.87	10.11
6h	220-22	—	—	15.00	11.47
		—	—	14.71	11.13
6i	190	68.80	4.66	15.00	11.47
		68.63	4.52	14.86	11.62
6j	194-95	72.38	4.00	—	10.16
		72.62	3.88	—	9.83
6o	176-77	63.16	3.76	21.00	12.00
		62.87	3.56	20.81	11.68
6p	182-83	52.90	2.90	20.59	23.53
		52.66	2.76	20.42	23.22

TABLE 3—2-(N-ARYL CARBOXAMIDOMETHYL
SULPHONYL)BENZOXAZOLES (7)

Compd. No.	m.p. °C	Analysis% ; Calcd./Found			
		C	H	N	S
7a	130-31	45.56	2.78	7.08	8.10
		45.11	2.61	7.16	8.12
7b	179-80	49.85	3.04	11.63	8.35
		49.15	3.12	11.55	8.71
7c	112-13	62.29	3.82	7.65	8.74
		62.72	3.61	7.41	8.22
7d	190-95d	53.33	3.33	7.77	8.88
		53.21	3.12	7.66	8.18

stretching frequencies, respectively, in addition to the $-\text{SO}_2-$ bands¹⁵ appearing at 1360-1340 cm^{-1} and 1160-1150 cm^{-1} .

Biological activity: Compounds of type (3a-f and 3l) were screened for their inhibitory effects against *Bacillus megatherium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Penicillium notatum* by agar diffusion technique¹⁶. Most of the screened compounds showed from 20-70% inhibition at a concentration of 0.1 mg/ml.

The more active compounds against *Bacillus megatherium* are 3a and 3c, against *Staphylococcus albus* is 3a and against *Aspergillus flavus* and *Penicillium notatum* are 3a and 3e and 3l, respectively.

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